

Preliminary evaluation of potential pathogenic fungi as bioherbicides of barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) in China

S.W. Huang, China National Rice Research Institute (CNRI); A.K. Watson, IRRI; G.F. Duan, and L.Q. Yu, China Rice Research Institute, Hangzhou 310006, China E-mail: ylq@zgb.com.cn

This study evaluated the use of pathogenic fungi in the biological control of barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), which has been rated as the most serious weed in rice (Holm et al 1977). From 1997 to 1999, more than 10 pathogenic fungi were isolated from naturally infected barnyardgrass leaves collected from different rice-growing areas in China. Preliminary bioassays show that *Exserohilum monoceras* (EM) and *Drechslera monoceras* (DM) are the most pathogenic to barnyardgrass. Further evaluation of these fungi as biocontrol agents was also conducted.

Fungi cultured for 7 d on potato dextrose agar were used as seed inoculum. Conidia were mass-produced on a barnyardgrass seed solid substrate (Huang et al 1999). Three pieces of agar plugs from the margins of young colonies were transferred to sterilized substrates and then incubated at 28 °C in the dark. Conidia were harvested 14 d after incubation by shaking the

flask with 50 mL of 0.05% Tween 20 distilled water, suspensions of which were filtered through a layer of cheesecloth. Conidia concentrations were determined with a hemacytometer.

To quantify the virulence of these two isolates on barnyardgrass, germinated seeds (coleoptile and radicle just emerged) were direct-seeded (10 seeds pot⁻¹) in plastic pots filled with saturated soil. Pots were placed in the greenhouse at 35/25 ± 5 °C day/night temperatures with natural light. Seedlings at 1.5–2.0-, 3.0–3.5-, and 4.5–5.0-leaf stages were inoculated by spraying 50 mL m⁻² of suspension of 10⁶ conidia mL⁻¹. After spraying, pots were placed in a dark dew chamber with more than 95% relative humidity (RH) at 28 °C for 24 h. Subsequently, pots were returned to the greenhouse and the RH was kept at 85–90% by spraying water. Disease reactions of barnyardgrass seedlings to two fungal isolates were evaluated 14 d after inoculation. Observation and re-

coding followed the methods and standards of Zhang et al (1996). The experimental design was a randomized complete block with three replications. The control treatment was sprayed with distilled water containing only Tween 20.

A similar experiment was conducted to determine the pathogenicity of these two fungi to plants other than barnyardgrass. All experimental methods in the host range test were the same as in the virulence test, except for plant growth stage at inoculation. The Fabaceae and Brassicaceae species were at the first true leaf stage and the Poaceae species were at the 1.5–2.0-leaf stage.

Disease incidence (DI, percentage of infected plants) of EM in barnyardgrass seedlings at the 1.5–5.0-leaf stage was more than 90% (Table 1). Seedlings at the 3.0–3.5-leaf stage were the most susceptible to EM, reaching 99.6% DI and more than 80% mortality. The DM isolate had 97.5–100% DI in barnyardgrass seedlings at all

Table 1. Virulence of potential biological control fungi on barnyardgrass seedlings at different growth stages.

Fungus	1.5–2.0 leaf					3.0–3.5 leaf					4.5–5.0 leaf				
	DI ^a (%)	MR (%)	LAD (%)	PH (cm)	FW ^b (%)	DI ^a (%)	MR (%)	LAD (%)	PH (cm)	FW ^b (%)	DI ^a (%)	MR (%)	LAD (%)	PH (cm)	FW ^b (%)
EM	91.8 b	85.4 a	46.7 a	14.3 b	48.4 a	99.6 a	81.5 a	63.8 a	15.6 b	65.1 a	95.4 b	77.2 a	53.3 a	15.9 b	57.1 a
DM	100.0 a	75.2 b	42.6 b	14.2 b	40.8 b	99.7 a	73.4 b	57.6 b	14.8 c	41.7 b	97.5 a	70.7 b	53.8 a	16.0 b	37.8 b
Control	4.3 c	0 c	3.3 c	17.5 a	3.3 c	5.9 b	0 c	1.8 c	19.1 a	4.8 c	5.8 c	0 c	1.7 b	19.8 a	5.2 c

^aDI = disease incidence, MR = mortality rate, LAD = leaf area damage, PH = plant height, FW = fresh weight reduction. ^bValues in the control line of FW are av fresh weights of pots. Values in the same column followed by different letters are significantly different at $P < 0.05$ according to ANOVA and the LSD test.

leaf stages tested. The 1.5–2.0-leaf stage was the growth stage most susceptible to DM (100% DI), with a mortality of 70.7–75.2%. The percentage leaf area damage (LAD, excluding dead plants) on seedlings caused by both fungi was not as high as expected. EM and DM significantly inhibited the height of barnyardgrass seedlings at different leaf stages. Other experiments have indicated that LAD and mortality rates were positively correlated with inoculum dose and duration of the dew period after inoculation.

Under greenhouse conditions and when applied at an inoculum dose of 5.0×10^7 conidia

m^{-2} , EM and DM were not pathogenic to rice seedlings (including indica, japonica, and hybrid rice) and to most other crops tested (Table 2). However, sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) was susceptible to EM and slightly susceptible to DM, and maize (*Zea mays*) was also slightly susceptible to EM. Barnyardgrass was the only plant species highly susceptible to these fungi, with EM causing plant death.

Preliminary results indicated the potential of DM and EM pathogens in controlling barnyardgrass, but further research is required to assess the risks to nontarget plant species

and to evaluate performance under field conditions.

References

- Holm LG, Plucknett DL, Pancho JV, Herberger JP. 1977. The world's worst weeds: distribution and biology. Honolulu, Hawaii. (USA): The University Press of Hawaii.
- Huang S, Yu L, Watson AK. 1999. Study of conidia production characterization of barnyardgrass fungi *Alternaria alternata* and *Curvularia lunata*. In: Proceedings of the 6th Weed Science Conference of China, 19-21 Mar 1999, Nanning, China. p 165–169.
- Zhang WM, Moody K, Watson AK. 1996. Responses of *Echinochloa* species and rice (*Oryza sativa*) to indigenous pathogenic fungi. Plant Dis. 80(9):1053–1058.

Table 2. Susceptibility of selected crop plants to potential biological control fungi of barnyardgrass.^a

Crop	EM	DM	Control	Crop	EM	DM	Control
<i>Zea mays</i>	ls	ns	ns	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	ns	ns	ns
<i>Glycine max</i>	ns	ns	ns	<i>Brassica napus oleifera</i>	ns	ns	ns
<i>Vigna sesquipedalis</i>	ns	ns	ns	<i>Oryza sativa</i> Jiayu 293 (indica)	ns	ns	ns
<i>Vicia faba</i>	ns	ns	ns	<i>O. sativa</i> Xiushui II (japonica)	ns	ns	ns
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	s	ls	ns	<i>O. sativa</i> Xieyou 46 (hybrid rice)	ns	ns	ns
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	ns	ns	ns	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	d	hs	ns

^ans = not susceptible; ls = lightly susceptible, with a few and small lesions on leaves; s = susceptible; hs = highly susceptible with many and expanded lesions on the leaves; d = dead plant. EM = *Exserohilum monoceras*, DM = *Drechslera monoceras*.

Response of two rice cultivars to competition from *Echinochloa crus-galli*

S. Pheng, School of Land and Food, University of Queensland, St. Lucia, Queensland 4072, Australia; G.C. Jahn, IRRI; and B. Khiev and C. Pol, Crop Protection Program, Cambodian Agricultural Research and Development Institute (CARDI), P.O. Box 01, Phnom Penh, Cambodia E-mail: s800661@student.uq.edu.au, g.jahn@cgiar.com, kbunnarith@bigpond.com.kh

Barnyardgrass [*Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv.] is an important weed of rice in irrigated and rainfed ecosystems in Cambodia. Rice yields decrease as barnyardgrass populations increase (Smith 1968). To minimize weed competition, Cambodian farmers transplant rice and practice hand-weeding (Jahn et al

1997). The success of this method depends on the amount of standing water after transplanting and the critical period of weeding. Unpredictable rainfall does not favor the use of water in weed management. In addition, labor for hand-weeding is becoming scarce because of competition from other industries. Although

herbicides can be used as a labor-saving option, they are expensive and may cause health and environmental hazards if incorrectly applied. In low-input farming systems such as those in Cambodia, competitive rice cultivars may be an important part of weed management.